

SAMPLE OF THE THEMATIC ANALYSIS

TABLE 1: Samples of the thematic analysis of the survey responses

Phase 1: Coding	
Survey response	Extracted codes
I'm a remote developer and enjoy the social community aspect of the groups and also value the immediate nature of the discussions when trying to solve a problem that generally aren't as fluid in other forums like StackOverflow	Socializing, Immediacy
To make sure people get answers to difficult / frustrating problems when using my software and as a feedback loop for what is and isn't working well in the software.	Help users, Issue Discovery
Sometimes docs are incomplete, ambiguous or too voluminous to read in it's entirety just to get started.	Inadequate documentation
Contributors communicate in real-time about issues/ideas and it's a quick way to gut-check an idea before putting together a full PR	Interactive, Brainstorm features
Yes. I trust in the Angular gitter community to guide me to the right approach in creating my application. This is extremely helpful in a fast growing language/technology where tutorials and resources from even a few months may already be outdated.	Custom feedback, Outdated documentation
Phase 2: Generating themes	
Codes	Theme
Socializing	Community
Immediacy, Interactive	Response time
Brainstorm features, Issue discovery	Project Tasks
Outdated documentation, Inadequate documentation	Documentation
Help users, Custom feedback	User support